

D1.3 Data management plan & ethical guidelines

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Deliverable information sheet

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0.2	06/06/2025	CERTH, WP leaders, pilot leaders	Contributions to the document
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Executive summary

Project summary

Shift2Zero, Shifting to zero-emission logistics through right-sized, mission-focused, N1 e-LCVs

Current market dynamics in EU reveal a gap between supply - existing N1 vehicles, and demand - evolving needs of urban logistics and climate targets. In 2023, 1.2M new LCV registrations were diesel-powered, and only 108,200 battery electric. Last-mile logistics, the least efficient and most complex part of the supply chain, presents significant opportunities for improvements at vehicle and operations levels. Dynamic requirements and increasing environmental impact require innovative solutions from the automotive industry, both from high volume OEMs and new entrants. S2Z aims to capitalize on the benefits of both vehicle platforms in the N1 segment - represented by IVECO's eDaily multipurpose platform, and Alke's ATX design-for-purpose platform - ultimately contributing to "Shifting to zero-emission logistics through right-sized, mission-focused, N1 e-LCVs".

To achieve this vision, S2Z proposes a 4-step user- and mission-centric design approach placing end-users and their needs at the core of all project activities. To this end, S2Z involves 5 LSPs & mobility operators as partners: Gruber, DHL, Diakinisis, Clem, DPD. As a result, S2Z will co-develop and shape at least 6 novel N1 concepts with enhanced and safe functionalities leading to tighter market fit, particularly in the segments of e-commerce, returns and cold deliveries.

Innovative concepts, from modular cargo bodies to vehicle control strategies with optimized tyres & brakes, as well as dual transport of people & freight, will be physically prototyped and tested in real-life operations in 6 pilot sites (Belgium, Greece, Italy, 2 in Norway, Poland).

S2Z brings a multidisciplinary consortium of 30 partners from 10 countries to cover the complete automotive and logistics value chains, complemented by policymakers to effectively ensure route to market: overcoming barriers for the adoption of S2Z eLCVs, reducing operational costs and environmental impact in scalable urban & sub-urban operations.

This deliverable D1.3 is the main output from **Task 1.2 – Quality, data management & ethics**, which will ensure the highest standards of quality, data management, and ethics throughout the project, safeguarding the integrity of research and adhering to Horizon Europe guidelines.

The quality management handled in this task is comprised into the deliverable D1.1, Project Management Plan. The general ethical management /Responsible Research & Innovation) and linked guidelines and templates are described within D1.1, Project Management Plan and Project Handbook. The data management related ethics considerations are described in this deliverable D1.3. Other aspects of ethics management, such as Humans (recruitment, informed consent etc.), POPD (Protection of Personal Data), non-EU countries and Artificial Intelligence, are explained in D1.1 SHIFT2ZERO Project Management Plan and Handbook. Their periodic report will be included in this deliverable D1.3, in months 18, 36 and 42.

In addition, a specific **task, T5.1 – Data requirements, governance models & KPIs alignment towards pilots evaluation** will work on the requirements from a data perspective (structure and semantics). The outcomes of this task will be included in D5.1 and cross-references in the next release of D1.3.

Management of data is an important element of multi-disciplinary projects. This document aims to be used by all the project partners, and in particular the Data Protection Officers of each partner and any partner involved in the collection or use of

data during the project. D1.3 goal is to guide partners in data management, providing regulations, protocols and templates to be used during the project.

As Shift2Zero will be collecting, using and generating a heterogeneous set of data throughout its lifecycle, D1.3 summarizes the types of data that will be generated and/or gathered during the project, the standards that will be used, the ways in which data will be exploited and shared (for verification or reuse), and in which way data will be preserved.

More specifically the following points are addressed:

- The guiding principles for data management in the project
- Data Summary, including an overview of what data will be gathered and processed in the project
- Provisions and principles for findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (FAIR) Data Management
- Allocation of resources and the costs for data management in this project, as well as the governance of data management within the project
- Provisions for data security as well as the adherence to the General Data Protection Directive (GDPR)
- Ethical aspects of data management, the Shift2Zero privacy strategy as well as IPR issues.

The Data Management Plan (DMP) provides a framework for good data handling by identifying the research data that the project expects to generate and describing which parts of the data can be shared with the public. Furthermore, it provides guidelines on naming conventions and metadata, storage of research data and steps to make them publicly available.

Shift2Zero will make use of open research data repositories such as Zenodo to comply with the Horizon Europe Open Access policy. Public deliverables, publications and anonymized datasets will be made available with open access. Datasets generated by Shift2Zero will be given persistent identifier (Digital Object Identifier, DOI), supplied with relevant metadata referencing the project name and grant agreement number.

The **Data Manager (DM)** describes data management mechanisms that are linked to all data requirements, collection, recording and organization, storage, retrieval, consultation and use, adaptation and alteration, permissions and access. S/he will ensure that the relevant GDPR regulations will be applied. Due to its nature, linked to the progress of project activities linked with data, this is a living document that will be updated periodically. Each partner assigns a **Data Protection Officer** as the person responsible for managing the project data accordingly in their entity.

This live document is updated during the project. Needed updates on data management and ethics management will be included in **updated versions of D1.3 in Month 18, Month 36, and Month 42**. This deliverable will be the base for all the Shift2Zero work involving data collection and analysis, particularly WP5, with the D5.1 Data models and KPIs definition, where data models requirements and specifications from multiple data sources will be documented.

Annex A provides traceability on the updates in the different versions.

D1.3 is submitted in line with the Grant Agreement, without any delays or differences in scope, goals and contents.

This deliverable follows a methodology that was developed by EUT, based on its large experience in coordinating European R&D projects, and which has demonstrated effectiveness, in particular in projects with large consortia and multidisciplinary teams.

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Terminology and Acronyms

A&FM	<i>Administrative and Financial Manager</i>
API	<i>Application Programming Interface</i>
APM	<i>Automated Parcel Machine</i>
CA	<i>Consortium Agreement</i>
CINEA	<i>European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency (the funding agency)</i>
D	<i>Deliverable</i>
DISSM	<i>Dissemination Manager</i>
DM	<i>Data Manager</i>
DMP	<i>Data Management Plan</i>
DoA	<i>Description of the Action</i>
DPO	<i>Data Protection Officers</i>
EC	<i>European Commission</i>
(e)HDV	<i>(electric) Heavy Duty Vehicle</i>
(e)LCV	<i>(electric) Light Commercial Vehicle</i>
EC	<i>European Commission</i>
E&DC	<i>Exploitation & Dissemination Committee</i>
E&IM	<i>Exploitation and Innovation Manager- IPR Advisor</i>
EU	<i>European Union</i>
FP	<i>Framework Programme</i>
GA	<i>General Assembly</i>
GDPR	<i>General Data Protection Regulation</i>
IPR	<i>Intellectual Property Rights</i>
KER	<i>Key Exploitable Result</i>
KPI	<i>Key Performance Indicator</i>
LCA	<i>Life Cycle Assessment</i>
LEZ	<i>Low Emission Zone</i>
MS	<i>Milestone</i>
OEM	<i>Original Equipment Manufacturer</i>
PC	<i>Project Coordinator</i>
PM	<i>Project Manager</i>
PMB	<i>Project Management Board</i>
POPD	<i>Protection of Personal Data</i>
QAP	<i>Quality Assurance Procedure</i>
RP1	<i>1st reporting period</i>
RP2	<i>2nd reporting period</i>
RP3	<i>3rd reporting period</i>
S2Z	<i>Shift2Zero</i>
TC	<i>Technical Coordinator</i>
TRL	<i>Technology Readiness Level</i>

WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leaders
ZEZ	Zero Emission Zone

1. Scope and purpose

1.1 Objectives of the deliverable

The purpose of this deliverable is to define the project's approach to data lifecycle management and ensure compliance with Horizon Europe's Open Science requirements. It aims to provide clear guidance for partners on handling data in accordance with FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable), as well as with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) and any other applicable legal or ethical obligations.

This DMP is a *living document*, intended to evolve over the project's duration. Updates will be incorporated in line with technical developments and reflected in the project's periodic reports.

1.2 Structure of the deliverable

The deliverable is organized to:

- Describe the types of data that will be collected, generated, and reused within Shift2Zero;
- Explain how this data will be stored, accessed, shared, and preserved;
- Present the methodology for ensuring openness, quality, and long-term value of the data assets;
- Outline the roles, responsibilities, and tools used across the project for data management;
- Provide practical details on datasets collected by each partner and their status.

2. Data summary

2.1 Data Categories

We provide information categorize data with respect to their origin being primary or secondary dataset:

- Primary data: new data collected in the duration of the SHIFT2ZERO project e.g., data generated from the testing activities, etc.
- Secondary data: already existing data relevant to SHIFT2ZERO e.g., datasets that can be found in open databases, already available test data from the lab, data from partners / former projects, CAVs trials, etc.

The categories of data to be used/generated by SHIFT2ZERO are summarised as follows:

Table 1. Data categories.

Data categories	
Primary data	<p>Primary data from users' and stakeholders' participation in SHIFT2ZERO:</p> <p>Workshops and stakeholders' engagement activities (WP8), design data (use cases, requirements, architectures), development data (computer code, source code), validation tests, metadata (technical WPs), Personal interviews (WP2-8), Engagement activities, dissemination and clustering aims with all related stakeholders, including the Website contact (WP8) form, data that may be collected in real time during the five pilots (WP6).</p>
Secondary data	<p>Secondary data:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - From partners - From outside the consortium <p>(Statistics, data from Apps and industrial companies, traffic, vehicles, fleets, research studies, open-source libraries used, standards, existing datasets from European projects, etc.) (all the WPs).</p>

2.2 Data in Shift2Zero

Apart from the examples of primary and secondary datasets used or generated in the project, from a technical level, the following examples of data will be handled in Shift2Zero:

- Vehicle performance measurements: battery consumption, trajectory coordinates, temperature control, speed, acceleration, elevation, charging time, emissions from tyres and brakes, measurements of forces (efforts), accelerations and other tyres parameters, braking distance for performance trade-off affecting grip, data energy use variables, physical properties of structural materials etc.
- Delivery mission profiles that include coordinates of delivery point, time-windows, weight, dimensions, temperature zone, special characteristics, traffic status, etc.

- Accidents, mechanical failures, battery and electronics failures, other unexpected incidents at full documentation
- Data for LCA (Life Cycle Assessment), TCO analysis (operational costs, pricing etc.).

A specific task, Task 5.1 – Data requirements, governance models & KPIs alignment towards pilots' evaluation will work on the requirements from a data perspective (structure and semantics). This demands the integration of diverse multifunctional data sources, from operational (trip planning, travel and stop times, hours of rest for drivers, etc.), economic (components of the vehicles' TCO) and technical variables (driving autonomy, charging times, payload, freight/goods specific temperature requirements, etc.). At the submission stage of this first release, Task 5.1 is still coordinating with WP2 for a proper data collection. The results of this task will be documented in D5.1 and cross-referenced in the next releases of D1.3.

3. FAIR Data management

Shift2Zero will generate data of different nature (project results, deliverables, research & development data, etc.) during its implementation, with potential for re-use and verification.

Partners are well experienced in FAIR¹ data principles and will further elaborate on these aspects in the appropriate deliverables and reports, to make all data collected, produced and processed findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable.

3.1 Making data Findable

Data collected from interviews, focus groups, brainstorming sessions, surveys or pilot experiments will be properly stored by each partner in charge of the related activity. Each project partner within its competences and available infrastructure and following their normal GDPR compliant practice of their organization, will ensure secure storage, delivery, and access of information they collect, as well as managing the rights of the users. Each partner through their Data Protection Officer (DPO) will thus handle each activity involving collection and process of data. This means all data collected will be processed in partners' systems/servers, protected by its own IT infrastructure. This information will be accessed only by the partners in charge of their collection and processing, so that they can appropriately manage the different project activities.

Information relevant to all consortium partners will be available on the Shift2Zero SharePoint and MS TEAMS; this also includes presentation slides, reports and deliverables.

The data collected and generated from online platforms will be made available using Digital Object Identifier (DOI) offered by open-access repositories (e.g., Zenodo). In case that the data collected has some data-sharing restrictions we will apply the methods established on "Terms and Conditions". We will provide full, detailed metadata (descriptive, administrative, and structural) for each dataset following the standards (e.g., DataCite Metadata Schema 4.3), and ensuring that this metadata is machine-readable.

In terms of communications, data collected from newsletters will be stored in the platform used for distribution Mailchimp. Website analytics are retrieved from Matomo, a tool monitoring all the traffic and obtain, periodically, reports about the site's performance. Instead of Google Analytics, Matomo does not compromise data security and privacy, guaranteeing full data ownership and that none of it is ever sent to other services and third parties.

All the scientific publications in journals or conferences will be identified with a DOI and the data used for generating this research will be published in open data repositories whenever possible to accomplish with security and privacy recommendations.

¹ FAIR data are data which meet principles of findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability

3.1.1 Naming Convention Strategy

Each data source will be provided with a specific name that will be composed by different parts/elements, containing information about pilot country, data type or format and naming structure as follows: TOD _ FORMAT _Info _VERSION

- TOD: The type of data
- FORMAT: The data format/extension
- Info: Additional (abbreviated) information about the dataset including companies providing the data.
- VERSION: The version of the dataset.

3.1.2 Version Numbering Strategy

A data versioning strategy similar to software versioning will be followed by applying a two-part numbering rule: Major. Minor (e.g. V1.1). Major data revision indicates a change in the formation and/or content of a dataset that may bring changes in scope, context or intended use. For example, a major revision may increase or decrease the statistical power of a collection, require change of data access interfaces, or enable or disable answering of research questions. A Major revision may incorporate:

- substantial new data items added to /deleted from a collection
- data values changed because temporal and/or spatial baseline changes
- additional data attributes introduced
- changes in a data generation model
- format of data items changed
- major changes in upstream datasets.

Minor revisions often involve quality improvement over existing data items. These changes may not affect the scope or intended use of initial collection. A Minor revision may include:

- renaming of data attribute
- correction of errors in existing data
- re-running a data generation model with adjustment of some parameters
- minor changes in upstream datasets.

3.1.3 Metadata & Search keywords

All datasets that will be openly available will be accompanied with metadata information in order to render them findable by interested third parties. A set of search keywords will be provided and will be part of the related metadata for each dataset.

At this point we plan to use the [CERIF](#) metadata format. However, in the course of the project we will check and identify any other applicable formats.

3.2 Making Data Accessible

3.2.1 Datasets

Data generated by the project will be made publicly available when possible. This means that open datasets and other information will be made public to a certain extent - on the condition that these data are anonymized, so there will be no recognizable patterns or (personal) information that could identify data subjects.

In reference to the nature of the user data involved, some of the results that will be generated by each project phase will be restricted to authorized users, while other results will be publicly available. Data access and sharing activities will be rigorously implemented in compliance with the privacy and data collection rules and regulations, as they are applied nationally and in the EU.

Some datasets that will be used for the purposes of the project are accessible from previous studies, already open to the public, while others are proprietary and have high commercial sensitivity. In cases where private data is processed and aggregated (e.g. as part of a model, or functionality of a component) permission will be needed from the provider prior to making the altered data publicly available.

Reports, deliverables, and other information for public distribution will be available on Zenodo or other Shift2Zero communication channels. Raw data (recordings, notes, user data, etc.) will not be available for third parties.

Datasets characterized as “openly accessible” will be published in OpenAire: <https://www.openaire.eu>.

3.2.2 Scientific Publications

The project partners are committed to make available research publications through Green Open Access where possible. Open access publications will be made available at the Shift2Zero website and Institutional portals. If applicable, Gold Open Access may be necessary, where the publication will be openly available through the publisher's website. The publications of the project will be disseminated through the project's dissemination and exploitation channels and follow the process described in the relevant project strategies.

3.2.3 Source code

It will be at the discretion of individual consortium members to decide whether the source code of their developed software is openly accessible. In such cases, different free and open-source software licenses will be investigated and the appropriate one will be selected. Open-source code from the Shift2Zero project will be made available through a source code repository such as GITLAB.

Since the DMP is expected to mature during the project, the subsequent releases of the deliverable will specify the repositories where the data will be stored and go into more detail on how this data can be accessed by the wider research community.

3.3 Making data Interoperable

Shift2Zero partners will use metadata vocabulary, when possible, to render the provided datasets interoperable. The formats that will be used will be described in later versions of the data management plan, based on the most common data formats: *.docx, *.pdf, *.mp4, *.mp3, *.jpg, *.csv, *.xlsx, *.json, *.txt; collected through interviews, focus groups, surveys, pilot experiments, etc.

All data must be stored properly - data for consortium partners will be accessible on SharePoint and/or MS TEAMS.

Task 5.1 – Data requirements, governance models & KPIs alignment towards pilots' evaluation will work on the requirements from a data perspective (structure and semantics). This demands the integration of diverse multifunctional data sources, from operational (trip planning, travel and stop times, hours of rest for drivers, etc.), economic (components of the vehicles' TCO) and technical variables (driving autonomy, charging times, payload, freight/goods specific temperature requirements, etc.).

3.4 Making data Reusable

Public reports, deliverables, non-sensitive- and anonymized data will be available for the public and third parties.

Non-sensitive or, if necessary, anonymized research data collected, produced, and processed during the project, will be published by default with previous data privacy and confidentiality compliance check by the data owners-generators, in open-access repositories (e.g., Zenodo) with a clear and accessible data usage license (e.g. CC-BY license²). The consortium will follow the same criteria for all the data unless third-party data requires a particular license. In case that the data is used for research publication, the consortium will also apply an embargo until the research is published. The data produced in Shift2Zero is available for third parties during an unlimited period, unless the collected data of platforms with "Terms and Conditions" does not allow it.

The metadata, market research data and any data needed to complete the project tasks will be, subject to any GDPR-advised modifications shared within the consortium.

Other forms of data reuse will be discussed in the development of the project in agreement with the consortium and following the requirements set by the different WPs.

The procedures and recommendations provided by SHIFT2ZERO if any, will also be applied.

The following table summarizes high-level categories of data.

Table 2. Summary of FAIR High-level categories.

Data category	FAIR	Description	Dissemination level
Documents and dissemination materials: Includes	F	Self-archive on website, and/or green scientific publications + OPENAIRE repositories	Public and confidential

² <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

deliverables, reports, demonstrations, new recordings, manuscripts, productions for dissemination, communication purposes.	A	Open Access by default policy, subject to exception (e.g., confidential deliverables)	
	I	Common text, image, or video formats (*.pdf, *.docx, *.jpeg, *.mov, *.avi, etc.)	
	R	Open Licences by default (attribution, non-commercial use)	
Computer software: including software applications (in binary form), libraries in the form of SDKs, plugins, and respective source code.	F	A project repository will be used, including meta-data and mechanisms for quick search of libraries, plugins, or generated software.	Public and confidential
	A	The Project repository includes the access control mechanisms necessary during its execution, and easily accessible from the development SDKs.	
	I	Binary formats, and ZIP files. Common programming languages will be used for the generated code (Python, NodeJS, C, Julia, Rust, etc.) and standard protocols, in order to guarantee integration by any OEM or supplier in the e-mobility sector.	
	R	Open Licences by default (research, non-commercial use)	
Research data and metadata: materials and datasets resulting from the implementation of the developments; metadata and configuration files; bug logs and feedback logs; developer internal documentation; evaluation and opinions.	F	A Project repository will be used to control access to data and information that must be protected to ensure confidentiality and security in its handling.	Public and confidential
	A	Required authentication and authorization mechanisms for access to the data collected are included to guarantee the privacy and confidentiality of the data collected and generated.	
	I	Accepted formats in the areas of 2ZERO and automotive sector are used in order to guarantee interoperability between the different tools, as well as evolution and improvements in the next stages of research and development, and integration by OEMs and providers.	
	R	Open Licences by default (research, non-commercial use)	
Data for evaluation: consists of materials or datasets generated or collected by the project used for evaluation	F	A repository will be used for data from the validation process of the tools in the different scenarios, so that they can be shared in different 2ZERO research projects.	Public and confidential

purposes. It may include personal data and information of participants in pilots and stakeholder engagement activities-	A	The access control mechanisms defined in the procedures and guidelines generated in 2ZERO project will be adopted.	
	I	The data format of this repository will follow the guidelines indicated in the 2ZERO project.	
	R	Open Licenses by default (research, non-commercial use), following the procedures and good practice guidelines from the 2ZERO project.	

4. Data collection and storage

4.1 Tools and methods

In shift2Zero, data collection methods typically fall into two main categories: manual and automatic, each serving different types of research objectives and data needs.

4.1.1 Manual data collection

Manual methods involve human participation in gathering data. These approaches are commonly used for qualitative, behavioral, or social science-related aspects of projects. Typical techniques to be used include:

- Surveys and questionnaires (online or paper-based)
- Interviews (structured, semi-structured, or open)
- Workshops and focus groups
- Observations and field notes
- Expert assessments or stakeholder feedback sessions

Manual collection is particularly valuable for collecting perception, user experience, acceptance, and behavioral insights, especially in pilot demonstrations or stakeholder engagements.

4.1.2 Automatic data collection

Automatic methods rely on technological tools to gather data continuously or in real time, with minimal human intervention. These are especially relevant in technical, mobility, energy, and digital innovation projects, all related to Shift2Zero. Examples include:

- Sensors and monitoring devices (e.g., environmental, energy, or mobility sensors)
- Internet of Things (IoT) platforms and edge devices
- Data logs from software tools or applications
- Simulation and modeling outputs
- Automated data acquisition from public APIs or remote systems

Automatic data collection supports the capture of high-volume, time-sensitive, and structured datasets, enhancing scalability and reducing human error.

Manual data collection enriches context and stakeholder perspectives, while automatic data ensures technical accuracy and real-time monitoring.

4.2 Storage infrastructure

In Shift2Zero, the data storage infrastructure will ensure security, accessibility, scalability, and compliance with legal and ethical requirements, including the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). It must support both the secure management of sensitive data and the open sharing of public datasets– see next sections.

Data will be stored using a combination of:

- Secure institutional or partner servers for internal and sensitive data,
- Cloud-based collaboration platforms (e.g. SharePoint) for project-wide access, file versioning, and collaborative editing,
- Certified open-access repositories (e.g. Zenodo, OpenAIRE) for the publication of anonymized datasets and public deliverables, with persistent identifiers (DOIs) and proper metadata.

5. Data security and protection

To ensure the security and protection of sensitive data, Shift2Zero follows a robust strategy that integrates technical safeguards, controlled access, and strict regulatory compliance. Sensitive data is stored on encrypted servers with role-based access restrictions, ensuring that only authorized personnel can handle it. To maintain data integrity and ensure continuity, regular backups are performed.

All data processing complies with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), with each partner designating a Data Protection Officer (DPO) responsible for overseeing legal and ethical adherence (as detailed in subsequent sections).

Where relevant, data is anonymised or pseudonymised and retained only for the time necessary to fulfil project objectives. Secure deletion protocols are applied once data is no longer needed. Shift2Zero fully embraces the "user decides" principle: end-users retain sole control over which personal or private data may be used, and no information is processed or disclosed without their explicit consent. When user-related data must be referenced or published, it is always aggregated and anonymised to prevent identification of individuals.

All personal data managed by the project is stored only for the project's duration, protected through password access, and housed in secure environments. No data will be shared with entities outside the Shift2Zero consortium unless express consent is granted by the user. Each partner processes data within their own protected IT infrastructure, with access limited to personnel directly responsible for the relevant activities. The Data Management Leader, CERTH, provides coordination and guidance to ensure consistent application of these principles across the consortium.

Finally, for data collected via the Shift2Zero website, dedicated measures are in place, including privacy and cookie policies, which are outlined in Annexes C and D.

6. Ethical and legal considerations

The Shift2Zero project consortium has long and extensive experience in the conduct of ethically sound research in compliance with national legislation, EU legislation, respect for international conventions and declarations, and their own institutional requirements.

The overall responsibility for ethical governance of the project is handled by the Project Coordinator, and concerning data management to the appointed Data Manager (CERTH). The research will be carried out in accordance with the ethics and data protection legislation of the participating countries, European legislation, and international conventions, as well as international declarations and codes of conduct relevant to research activities which include:

- Committee of Ministers Council of Europe (1990). Recommendation (No. R(90)3).
- Conventions of the Council of Europe (Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Dignity of the Human Being)
- Universal Declaration of UNESCO (Universal Declaration on the and Human Rights, 11 November 1997).
- Charter of Fundamental Rights of the EU (signed in Nice, December 7, 2000, 2000/C364/01).
- The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR, Regulation (EU) 2016/679);
- And additional frameworks introduced under Horizon Europe, including the European Data Governance Act (Regulation (EU) 2022/868) and the forthcoming AI Act and Data Act, where applicable.

6.1 GDPR compliance

CERTH as Data Manager is responsible for the development of the ethical guidelines and procedures that must be followed throughout the Shift2Zero project to ensure full compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR - Regulation (EU) 2016/679). These guidelines are designed to guarantee that data subjects and data owners remain in control of their personal data, its use, and any subsequent processing. In particular, all data handling activities in Shift2Zero will uphold the core GDPR principles, including the protection of natural persons and the free movement of personal data.

The project adopts a twelve-step framework based on recommendations from the UK Information Commissioner's Office (ICO), aimed at ensuring data protection is embedded across all research and technical activities:

Step 1: Awareness. All partners, key personnel, and decision-makers in Shift2Zero have been informed of GDPR obligations. Supporting material has been provided to raise awareness of the regulation's impact on their respective roles.

Step 2: Information held. Beginning with this deliverable, the consortium will maintain detailed records of any personal data collected or processed, including data origin and sharing parties. These records will demonstrate compliance with the GDPR's accountability requirement, ensuring transparency and traceability.

Step 3: Communicating privacy information. Privacy notices provided to data subjects will adhere to GDPR standards. Users will be informed of the lawful basis for data processing, retention periods, their rights, and the procedures to lodge a complaint with Shift2Zero in case of concerns. All information will be conveyed in clear, concise, and accessible language.

Step 4: Individuals' rights. Shift2Zero ensures full respect for the rights of individuals, including access, rectification, erasure, restriction of processing, data portability, objection, and protection from automated decision-making and profiling.

Step 5: Subject access requests. The project will respond to personal data access requests within one month, free of charge. In cases where requests are manifestly unfounded or excessive, clear justification will be provided, along with details on how individuals can appeal to a supervisory authority.

Step 6: Lawful basis for processing. All data processing in Shift2Zero is grounded in a valid legal basis, primarily informed consent and the use of appropriate privacy notices.

Step 7: Consent. Informed consent procedures will fully comply with GDPR requirements. Consent will be freely given, specific, informed, and unambiguous, and collected independently from other terms and conditions. Participants will always be offered simple, accessible means to withdraw their consent at any time.

Step 8: Children. Although underage participation is not anticipated, any involvement of minors will require age verification and explicit parental or guardian consent before any data is processed.

Step 9: Data breaches. Shift2Zero has established mechanisms for the detection, reporting, and investigation of personal data breaches. If a breach poses significant risk to the rights and freedoms of individuals, those affected will be informed without undue delay.

Step 10: Data protection by design and DPIA. The project applies a privacy-by-design approach and will conduct Data Protection Impact Assessments (DPIAs) where necessary, especially when processing operations present high risks to data subjects.

Step 11: Data Protection Officers (DPOs). Each partner has designated a DPO responsible for overseeing GDPR compliance. These officers are empowered to ensure that all project activities, including volunteer recruitment and handling of sensitive data, are aligned with ethical and legal standards.

Step 12: Anonymisation and data minimisation. Where possible, data will be anonymised or pseudonymised before analysis or sharing, reducing the risk of re-identification. When user-related data is used for publication or reporting, it will always be aggregated and anonymised using reliable tools, ensuring individual privacy is preserved.

In accordance with the "user decides" principle, data subjects maintain full control over which personal data may be used. No personal information will be stored, processed, or shared outside the Shift2Zero consortium without explicit, prior consent. Furthermore, all personal data will be retained only for the duration of the project, and will be securely deleted thereafter following GDPR-compliant procedures.

6.2 Ethical review

To strengthen compliance with ethical and data management principles throughout the project, Shift2Zero implements two key internal procedures that frame data handling across all project activities and deliverables:

1. Ethics and Data Management Reminder at Task Kick-off

At the start of each task or deliverable, the respective Task Leader, with the support of the Work Package (WP) Leader, will conduct a short internal briefing to remind all contributors of the project's data management rules and ethical obligations. This includes:

- Identifying the activities in the task that are affected by ethics and data management
- Reviewing the types of data expected to be used or generated;
- Verifying whether informed consent, anonymisation, or data minimisation apply;
- Ensuring all partners are aware of relevant procedures from the Data Management Plan (D1.3) and the Ethics and Legal Framework (D1.1);
- Clarifying the roles and responsibilities for data storage, access control, and metadata documentation.

This pre-task ethics reminder ensures that data handling is ethically sound from the outset and that contributors proactively apply the project's GDPR-compliant practices.

2. Ethics and Data Compliance Check Before Deliverable Submission

Once a deliverable draft is complete, it will undergo a cross-reading review by one or more assigned reviewers, as part of Shift2Zero's internal quality assurance process. In addition to content and formatting checks, these cross-readers are explicitly tasked with verifying that:

- The deliverable summarizes that in the related task activities, ethical and data management have been considered when needed
- All references to personal or sensitive data comply with anonymisation or consent requirements;
- No confidential or user-identifiable data is included in public sections such as the Executive Summary;
- Data use is aligned with the stated access levels, licensing terms, and retention policies from the DMP;
- Proper metadata and dataset documentation are included or referenced where applicable.

If any issues are identified, feedback will be sent to the authors for revision prior to formal submission. This ethics compliance checkpoint reinforces data protection across all project outputs.

6.3 Intellectual Property Rights (IPR)

IPR will receive special attention from the beginning. All rules regarding management of knowledge and IPR will be governed by the Consortium Agreement (CA). Shift2Zero will be initially based on DESCA (CA Model) Horizon Europe model for the CA. Shift2Zero

will not act in contradiction with the rules laid down in Annex II of the Grant Agreement. The CA will address background and foreground knowledge, ownership, protected third party components of the products, and protection, use and dissemination of results and access rights. In this regard, the following principles will be applied:

- Confidentiality: During the project duration and beyond, the contractors shall treat any information, which is designated as property by the disclosing contractors, as confidential. They also shall impose the same obligations to their employees and suppliers.
- Pre-existing know-how: Each Contractor is and remains the sole owner of its IPR over its pre-existing know-how. The Contractors will identify and list the pre-existing know-how over which they may grant access rights for the project. The Contractors agree that the access rights to the pre-existing know-how needed for carrying out their own work under the project shall be granted on a royalty-free basis.
- Ownership and protection of knowledge: The ownership of the knowledge developed within the project will be governed by an open-source license.
- Open data: Data and results obtained during the project that are based on open public-sector data will be made available free of charge.

The procedures for the dissemination, protection and exploitation of IPR are covered in the CA (including sections 9.8.2 General principles and 9.8.3 Access to Software). IPR will be applied according to the rules of the employer under the applicable European and national laws and regulations.

7. Allocation of resources

CERTH, as Data Manager, with the support of EUT as Project Coordinator, is responsible for ensuring the implementation of the DMP. The Data Manager is Mr. Zisis Maleas.

On the other hand, each partner has assigned a Data Protection Officer (DPO) who will handle each activity involving collection and process of personal data. As such, staff time has been allocated in the proposed budget to cover the costs of preparing data and documentation for archiving. Specifically, 10 PMs are devoted to Task 1.2 Quality, data management & ethics, and 26,5 PMs to Task 5.1 Data requirements, governance models & KPIs alignment towards pilots' evaluation, from which a significant proportion is for data management.

All research data collected as part of Shift2Aero is owned by the respective partner who generated the dataset. The Principal Investigator of this project will take responsibility for the collection, management, and sharing of the research data as defined and outlined within this DMP.

In general, collected data and results will be either freely available or accessible for a reasonable cost. Reports or other written deliverables will be available on the Shift2Zero communications channels or other platforms. Data generated within the project outside of contacts and reports (e.g., audio/video, slides, etc.) will require an allocation of resources difficult to envision now. Storing- and long-term data preservation is possible but has not been discussed yet; hereby we cannot estimate the additional costs. All data collected by partners falls under partners' intellectual property.

8. Open access and repositories

8.1 Repositories used

To ensure secure, accessible, and FAIR-compliant dissemination of project outputs, Shift2Zero uses a combination of open and restricted repositories.

- Zenodo is the primary open-access repository for publishing public datasets, scientific deliverables, and peer-reviewed publications. It provides DOIs for long-term preservation and citation and is fully integrated with OpenAIRE and the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).
- For collaborative work and internal documentation, the project uses SharePoint, which offers controlled access for consortium partners.
- GitLab is employed to host and manage open-source code, models, and scripts developed during the project, ensuring version control and public reuse under appropriate licenses.
- Additionally, the Argos platform is used to create and maintain the project's machine-actionable Data Management Plan, aligned with Horizon Europe requirements and open for public access.

8.2 Access and licensing

Shift2Zero is committed to ensuring that all research outputs are made accessible in accordance with the Open Science principles and the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) data management approach promoted by Horizon Europe. Access to project results is governed by a structured policy that balances openness, legal obligations (e.g., GDPR), and intellectual property considerations.

Shift2Zero is conceived as integrated solutions that can also be standalone assets, including and/or use several products with different licensing models. It is therefore crucial to ensure that the licenses are compatible. The first step to achieve this goal is establishing the complete assets inventory defining license used for each product used within Shift2Zero. The licenses are yet to be decided, nevertheless, discussions are ongoing and actions to start alignment between partners are to be taken.

Each asset type—publications, datasets, software, and documentation—is assigned a specific access level and associated license to promote reuse while protecting sensitive or proprietary information.

Publications resulting from Shift2Zero will be made openly available in institutional or subject-specific repositories, with Zenodo as the preferred platform. These will be published under Creative Commons Attribution (CC-BY) licenses, allowing wide reuse with proper citation. Peer-reviewed articles will follow the Horizon Europe Open Access mandate, with no embargo period where possible. Metadata for all publications will be made public even if full access is temporarily restricted.

Research datasets will be published as openly as possible and as restricted as necessary. Datasets that do not contain sensitive or personal information will be shared on Zenodo with CC0 (public domain) or CC-BY licenses, promoting unrestricted reuse and attribution. When data contains personal, confidential, or security-sensitive information, controlled access mechanisms will be applied, including embargo periods,

anonymisation, or data sharing agreements. Metadata will still be published openly to ensure findability and transparency.

Software and code developed within the project will be shared, when possible, via GitLab under widely recognized open-source licenses such as MIT, Apache 2.0, or Eclipse Public License (EPL), depending on the component. Each repository will include documentation, versioning, and citation instructions to support reuse and community contributions. In some cases, private repositories may be used during development, with public release planned upon completion or validation.

Internal deliverables, draft documents, and confidential data will be stored and exchanged via the project's SharePoint platform, with access strictly limited to authorized consortium members. These documents will not be shared externally unless specifically approved and sanitized for public release.

Overall, the project's licensing strategy ensures that publicly funded research outputs are made **as openly accessible as possible, while fully respecting legal, ethical, and contractual obligations.**

All access conditions and licensing details will be documented in the project's Data Management Plan (DMP) and reviewed regularly throughout the project lifecycle.

9. Data register

Primary datasets will be registered using the following tables, according to their nature: documentation, datasets, computer software, publications. Publications will be compiled within the Shift2Zero SharePoint, in the WP8 Achieving route to impact, scalability and replication.

9.1 Documents

Documents include deliverables, reports and project dissemination materials.

Dataset number	DOC1
Dataset name	Project deliverables
Primary or Secondary	Primary
Partner	All partners
Description	Public deliverables will be accessible through the Shift2Zero website on a dedicated page and uploaded to Zenodo. Confidential deliverables will not be published but the executive summary will be shared on the Shift2Zero website. An info sheet with specific details on each pilot actions will be produced and publicly shared. An internal copy of all deliverables will be stored in the project's SharePoint account.
Relevant Task(s)	WP(s) - All Work packages
Format	*.pdf
Amount	500MB
Data sharing plan	Public deliverables: Shift2Zero website: https://shift2zero-project.eu/ Confidential deliverables: Shift2Zero repository (SharePoint)
Expected to be available	Indicated in the Grant Agreement

Dataset number	DOC2
Dataset name	Project dissemination videos
Primary or Secondary	Primary
Partner	All partners
Description	Videos for dissemination purposes about the project. Shift2Zero videos will be published on YouTube and on a page within Shift2Zero website. An internal copy will be kept inside the SharePoint account.
Relevant Task(s)	WP(s) - All work packages
Format	*.mp4
Amount	50GB
Data sharing plan	YouTube: https://www.youtube.com/@Shift2ZeroProject Shift2Zero website: https://shift2zero-project.eu/

Expected available	to	be	Period 1 of the project
Dataset number	DOC3		
Dataset name	Project materials to promote the project activities and raise awareness		
Primary or Secondary	Primary		
Partner	All partners		
Description	Flyers, brochures, catalogues, infographics, presentations, and other materials to disseminate the project. Promotional materials. All promotional materials will be able for download within Shift2Zero website, a copy will be saved in SharePoint.		
Relevant Task(s)	WP(s)	-	All work packages
Format	*.pdf		
Amount	100MB		
Data sharing plan	Shift2Zero website: https://shift2zero-project.eu/ Shift2Zero repository (SharePoint)		
Expected available	to	be	Period 1 of the project

9.2 Datasets

This category includes the creation of data from social media statistics, website analytics, newsletter subscribers, data from dissemination and communication activities, media outlets, project personal data collected for project events, etc.

Dataset number	DATA1		
Dataset name	Project social media statistics		
Primary or Secondary	Primary		
Partner	EUT		
Description	LinkedIn analytics for tracking the number of followers, likes, shares and monitor KPIs.		
Relevant Task(s)	WP(s)	-	WP8 – Task 8.1
Format	*.xml		
Amount	500kB		
Data sharing plan	Shift2Zero repository (SharePoint)		
Expected available	to	be	From the beginning of the project, only for Shift2Zero partners

Dataset number	DATA2		
Dataset name	Project website analytics		
Primary or Secondary	Primary		
Partner	EUT		

Description	Website data in terms of traffic (visits, pages viewed, users, time on page, etc.). The Shift2Zero website uses Matomo in the platform's backend which allows to monitor traffic and generate periodic performance reports prioritizing security and privacy, ensuring full data ownership and preventing any data from being shared with third parties.		
Relevant Task(s)	WP(s)	-	WP8 – Task 8.1
Format	*.xml		
Amount	5MB		
Data sharing plan	Shift2Zero repository (SharePoint), Matomo		
Expected to be available	From the creation of project website (M3), ,only for Shift2Zero partners		

Dataset number	DATA3		
Dataset name	Project newsletter subscriptions		
Primary or Secondary Partner	Primary EUT		
Description	Personal data of Shift2Zero newsletter subscribers to produce e-mail campaigns and newsletters distribution. Subscriptions will be possible through a Mailchimp sign up form . Data is closed to EUT due to GDPR as it includes personal data.		
Relevant Task(s)	WP(s)	-	WP8 – Task 8.1
Format	*.csv		
Amount	5MB		
Data sharing plan	EUT internal repository Mailchimp		
Expected to be available	From the beginning of the project, only for Shift2Zero partners		

Dataset number	DATA4		
Dataset name	Project data from dissemination and communication activities		
Primary or Secondary Partner	Primary EUT		
Description	This data will be collected through a periodic monitoring of the project's miscellaneous dissemination activities such as publications in relevant journals, social media posts, participation to conferences and events, etc. The data will consist of a list of dissemination and communication activities done by partners for a specific period. The purpose of collecting this data is to assess the outreach and efficiency of the dissemination activities during the implementation of the project. Data will be collected from partners through an internal Excel file. Data will be open to Shift2Zero partners during the project execution.		

Relevant Task(s)	WP(s)	-	WP8 – Task 8.1
Format			*.xml
Amount			5MB
Data sharing plan			Shift2Zero repository (SharePoint)
Expected to be available			Available from the beginning of the project, only for Shift2Zero partners

Dataset number	DATA5		
Dataset name	Project data from media outlets / journalists		
Primary or Secondary Partner	Primary		
Partner	EUT		
Description	A file with personal data for journalists and media outlets of interest will be created by EUT by filtering their media database. The database will be used for sending Shift2Zero press releases to the media and pithing project results. Data is closed, will be stored in an internal database for managing media relations in the project (coming from EUT media database).		
Relevant Task(s)	WP(s)	-	WP8 – Task 8.1
Format			*.xml
Amount			10MB
Data sharing plan			EUT internal database
Expected to be available			Available from the beginning of the project, only for Shift2Zero partners

Dataset number	DATA6		
Dataset name	Project personal data collected for project events (registrations /attendees)		
Primary or Secondary Partner	Primary		
Partner	EUT		
Description	Dataset on personal details of attendants / registrants to the stakeholder engagement events organized by Shift2Zero. Participants lists to manage their participation into project events. There is no data source, Formassembly will be used as data processor. Data in this dataset will be closed to event's organisers due to GDPR.		
Relevant Task(s)	WP(s)	-	WP8 – Task 8.1
Format			*.xml
Amount			10MB
Data sharing plan			EUT internal database hoster in Formassembly and Salesforce
Expected to be available			Available from the first event organised, only for Shift2Zero partners organizing each event

9.3 Research data and metadata

The category of research data and meta data regroups materials and datasets resulting from the implementation of the developments; metadata and configuration files; bug logs and feedback logs; developer internal documentation; evaluation and opinions.

Vehicle performance measurements: battery consumption, trajectory coordinates, temperature control, speed, acceleration, elevation, charging time, emissions from tyres and brakes, measurements of forces (efforts), accelerations and other tyres parameters, braking distance for performance trade-off affecting grip, data energy use variables, physical properties of structural materials (mechanical strength, ductility, toughness), PCMs (melting point, heat capacity, conductivity), and VIPs (thermal resistance, moisture behavior); delivery mission profiles that include coordinates of delivery point, time-windows, weight, dimensions, temperature zone, special characteristics, traffic status, etc.; accidents, mechanical failures, battery and electronics failures, other unexpected incidents at full documentation; Data for LCA (Life Cycle Assessment), for TCO analysis (operational costs, pricing etc.); etc.

This information feeds simulation models and validates results in SHIFT2ZERO.

9.4 Computer software

Computer software includes software applications (in binary form), libraries in the form of SDKs, plugins, and respective source code.

The Shift2Zero (S2Z) project will deliver an integrated fleet management platform incorporating advanced algorithms and simulation tools designed to address operational challenges and support pilot sites in planning optimized delivery operations. The platform will facilitate seamless interaction with participating pilot sites, including logistics companies and their delivery networks, enabling them to utilize the embedded tools to effectively plan dispatching schedules and charging processes in alignment with the innovative vehicle technologies developed within the project. Furthermore, the platform will be made publicly accessible, allowing third-party stakeholders to leverage its functionalities to support the decarbonisation and optimisation of their own fleets, thereby extending the impact of the S2Z innovations beyond the initial demonstrators. The software developed under S2Z will fully comply with applicable data protection regulations, including the GDPR, and will implement robust data anonymization techniques, role-based access control, and secure encryption protocols to ensure the confidentiality and integrity of sensitive user data. Transparency will be maintained through clearly defined data governance policies, user consent mechanisms, and regular audits, ensuring that all users retain control over their data and its use within the platform. The whole platform will be developed via open-source tools including Python, C#, and their related libraries.

9.5 Data for evaluation

The data for evaluation category consists of materials or datasets generated or collected by the project used for evaluation purposes. It may include personal data and information of participants in pilots and stakeholder engagement activities.

Within the framework of WP5, simulation models will be developed and executed through the S2Z platform to support fleet managers in evaluating strategic scenarios for the electrification of their assets. The simulation environment will serve as a virtual playground that replicates real-world operational conditions, enabling stakeholders to test and analyse various configurations and decision pathways. By generating synthetic yet realistic operational data, the models will provide insights into the expected impacts of integrating eLCV solutions, supporting organizations identify optimal strategies for embedding these innovations into their day-to-day logistics operations. The generated data will be provided to WP7 for impact assessment analysis and will be available publicly in the related deliverables.

In further updates of the Data Management Plan, this table will be filled for each main dataset:

Dataset number	Eval1
Dataset name	to be filled
Primary or Secondary	Primary
Partner	to be filled
Description	to be filled
Relevant WP(s) - Task(s)	WPx
Format	to be filled
Amount	to be filled
Data sharing plan	to be filled
Expected to be available	to be filled

10. Conclusions

The Shift2Zero DMP and ethical guidelines will be used by all partners and reflects the organizational measures and operational procedures applied for managing the data collected, produced or processed during the project for the partners.

As described in the DMP, the main data collected, produced and processed within the project has varied natures: (a) data from surveys, workshops, (b) data from the 5 main pilots; (c) contact data with personal information for communication and dissemination or workshops; (d) data for the project outcomes, etc. The partners will publish data in open repositories and made it available for the community whenever possible, especially research data. All the data managed in the project will be treated in accordance with GDPR.

This live document is updated during the project at the end of each reporting period, with the datasets generated in the period, and any relevant information on the Data Management of the cited period.

11. Annex A: summary of changes of updated versions

Table 3. Summary of changes in updated versions

Date of the update: June 2026 (Month 18)

Section	Change	Comments

Date of the update: December 2027 (Month 36)

Section	Change	Comments

Date of the update: June 2028 (Month 42)

Section	Change	Comments

12. Annex B: Data Protection Officer list per partner

The Data Protection Officers list is part of a confidential version of the deliverable, internal and accessible by the Shift2Zero consortium only.

13. ANNEX C: Shift2Zero website privacy notice

13.1 Preliminary information

FUNDACIÓ EURECAT considers your personal information is very important. We therefore process it confidentially and securely. We are committed to ensuring the privacy of personal data at all times and not to collect unnecessary information.

You do not need to previously sign up in order to access our website. If you require any further information, you can contact us through the form available on our website, providing you agree with our privacy policy, which you must accept in order to record your express consent to the data processing for the specified purposes.

Pursuant to Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of 27 April 2016 on the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data and Act 3/2018 of 5 December on the protection of personal data and guarantee of digital rights, we provide you with information about the processing of your data through this Privacy Policy.

13.2 Who process the data?

Identity: FUNDACIÓ EURECAT (hereinafter referred to as “Eurecat“)

Tax Identification Code (NIF): G66210345

Registered office: Parc Tecnològic del Vallès. Avinguda Universitat Autònoma, 23 – 08290 Cerdanyola del Vallès

Legal department email address: legal@eurecat.org

Telephone number: + 34 93 238 14 00

13.3 Data protection officer

Email address of the Data Protection Officer: dpo@eurecat.org

What data do we collect, for what purposes and for how long do we store them?

DATA PROCESSING PURPOSE AND LEGAL BASIS		STORAGE PERIOD
Contact form	To respond to requests and enquiries made by the user, the legal basis of the processing being the data subject's express consent pursuant to Article 6.1.a) of the GDPR.	The data collected will be stored for the time strictly necessary to fulfil the purpose for which they were collected and, in any case, to determine the possible liabilities that could arise from such purpose, taking into account the periods specified in the relevant regulations
Sending informative messages about the company and the Newsletter	To subscribe to information, promotions and offers of the company, the legal basis for the processing being the data subject's express consent pursuant to Article 6.1.a) of the GDPR.	The data will be stored for the period the data subject has subscribed to the Newsletter or until he/she exercises the right to object to or erase the data. However, they may be stored in order to

		determine the possible liabilities that could arise from such purpose
Email management	To respond to the enquiries received and to manage the commercial or professional relationship, the legal basis being the contractual relationship between the Data Controller and the data subject, pursuant to Article 6.1.b) of the GDPR	The data collected will be stored for the time strictly necessary to fulfil the purpose for which they were collected and, in all cases, to determine the possible liabilities that could arise from such purpose, taking into account the periods specified in the relevant regulations
Activities, conferences and events	To manage the registration to take part in activities, conferences or events. The data will be processed for such purpose, the legal basis of which is the data subject's express consent pursuant to Article 6.1.a) of the GDPR	The data will be stored for the time strictly necessary to fulfil the purpose for which they were collected and, in all cases, to determine the possible liabilities that could arise from such purpose, taking into account the periods specified in the relevant regulations

13.4 To whom will be the data disclosed?

Eurecat is the main recipient of user data, however, it may be accessible to third parties that develop services to the Data Controller. Those scenarios that required Eurecat service suppliers' access to the user's data, because of the services arranged, shall be submitted to the legal obligations, which are those of article 28 GDPR'S. In any event, Eurecat service suppliers shall not process the user's data for their own or different purposes and shall not overreach from the services purposes, and, in any case, shall not rent, sold, or make it available to third parties.

The Data Controller shall not transfer your data to third parties without your prior consent, which should fulfil the legal requirements.

The Data Controller in case of legal obligations may transfer your data to third parties, without the user prior consent.

The personal data obtained by the web forms may be transferred to certain consortium partners with whom Eurecat cooperate, for the purpose to manage and answer the user contact as well as to execute the proper actions to carry out the web form purposes for which the data was given This data access by the consortium partners, does not entail a data assignment for its own purposes. You may consult the detailed list of the project consortium partner [here](#).

13.5 Are data transferred internationally

There are no international data transfers to countries outside the European Union.

13.6 What are your rights as a user and how can you exercise them?

Right to access the data

As a user, you can ask us to explain what we do with your personal data. You can also ask us for information about the purpose of the processing of your personal data, the period of time for which we store them, your rights as a user, the transfer of the data to a third country or an international organisation, the existence of automated decisions or profiling on the website, among others.

Right to rectification

If the personal data you have provided to us are inaccurate or incomplete, you are entitled to rectify or supplement them. Please contact us and we will rectify the data according to your request.

Right to restrict the processing

As a user you can request restriction of the processing of your personal data in the following cases:

If you question the accuracy of your personal data, for a period of time that allows us to verify their accuracy.

If the processing is unlawful and you object to the erasure of your personal data, instead of erasure, you request that their use is restricted.

If we no longer need your data for the purposes of processing, but they are needed for the establishment, exercise or defence of legal claims.

Right to erase

You can request us to erase your personal data immediately. We are obliged to erase the data immediately if they are no longer required for the purpose for which they were collected. In addition, you can ask us to erase your data if you change your mind about the consent you granted, if you object to the processing and there are no justified grounds for it, if your data are processed incorrectly, if the data must be erased in order to comply with a legal obligation or if the data has been obtained related to a legal offer.

Right to information

If you have exercised a right to rectify, erase or restrict your data, we are obliged to inform all the recipients to whom your personal data have been disclosed of such rectification, erasure or restriction of processing, unless this proves impossible or involves a disproportionate effort. As a user, you are entitled to be informed by the data controller about who these recipients are.

Right to data portability

You are entitled to receive the personal data you have provided to us in a structured, commonly used and machine-readable format. You are also entitled to transfer this data to another data controller without us being able to prevent this.

Right to object to the data processing

As a user, you are entitled to object to our use of the personal data made available to us at any time for reasons related to your personal situation. We will stop processing your personal data unless we have compelling legitimate grounds to use them, if such

grounds override your interests, rights and freedoms or if the processing is for the establishment, exercise or defence of legal claims.

Right to withdraw the declaration of consent related to data protection

As a user you are entitled to change your declaration of consent related to data protection at any time. This change of decision regarding the consent will not affect the legality of the processing that took place on the basis of the consent provided prior to its withdrawal.

Automated individual decisions, including profiling

You are entitled not to be subject to a decision solely based on automated processing, including profiling, which has legal effects for you or significantly affects you in a similar way.

Right to submit a complaint to a supervisory authority

As a user you are entitled to submit a complaint to a supervisory authority, in particular in the Member State of your residence, place of work or place of infringement, if you consider the processing of your personal data implies a violation of the GDPR.

13.7 Where you can exercise your rights?

You can request to exercise your rights at the following e-mail address: legal@eurecat.org

13.8 Is it mandatory to provide all the information requested in the data collection forms?

Regarding the forms posted on the website, you must fill in the fields marked as “required”. Failure to complete the required personal data or only partial completion could mean that Eurecat will be unable to deal with your requests and, therefore, Eurecat will be held harmless for any liability due to not rendering or only partially rendering the requested services.

The personal data provided by the user to Eurecat must be current information so that our records are up to date and error-free. The user is responsible for the veracity of the data provided.

13.9 What security measures have we implemented?

Eurecat protects and uses your personal data according to the regulations in force on data protection and information society services.

We have implemented the necessary technical and organisational security measures to guarantee the security of the users’ personal data and prevent their alteration, loss, unauthorised processing and/or access thereto, bearing in mind the state of the art, the kind of data provided and the risks to which they could be exposed, whether due to human action or physical or natural factors, in accordance with the provisions in the regulations in force.

14. ANNEX D: Shift2Zero website cookies policy

14.1 What are cookies and what are they used for?

A cookie is a file that is downloaded to the user's device when they access certain websites which stores and retrieves information about the browsing activity on their computer.

Cookies allow this website, among other things, to store and retrieve information about the user's decisions and habits. Some of the cookies used on this website are necessary for it to function.

It is important to highlight that the use of cookies does not provide access to the user's personal data.

14.2 What kind of cookies exist?

Depending on the time they remain active, Cookies can be divided into session or persistent cookies.

- **Session cookies** are designed to collect and store data while the user accesses a website and are removed as soon the explorer is closed. They are normally used to store information which only needs to be kept in order to provide the service requested by the user on just one occasion.
- **Persistent cookies** remain stored on the device and can be accessed and handled during a period specified by the user of the cookie, which may be from a few minutes to several years.

Additionally, depending on the organization managing them, cookies may be classified as first-party or third-party cookies.

- **First-party cookies** are sent to the user's device from a computer or domain managed by the website publisher and are used to provide the service requested by the user.
- **Third-party cookies** are sent to the user's device from a computer or domain that is not managed by the website publisher, but by another organisation that handles data obtained from the cookies.

In terms of their purpose, the types of cookies are:

- **Technical cookies:** Technical cookies allow the user to browse a website, platform or application and use the different service options found there.
- **Profiling cookies:** Profiling cookies allow the user to access the service with some predefined general features based on a series of criteria on the user's device such as language, settings, etc.
- **Analytical cookies:** Analytical cookies allow the website owner to track and analyse user behaviour on the websites to which they are linked. The information collected is used to measure activity on the websites and to create users' browsing profiles, with the aim of introducing improvements.

- **Advertising cookies:** Advertising cookies allow the advertising spaces which the publisher puts on the website to be managed as efficiently as possible.

14.3 What kind of cookies does the website use?

The user may consult and set up the website cookies managed by the website publisher at Cookie settings.

The user should take account that although the cookies may be set up, certain cookies are needed and must be installed to ensure proper access and use of the website, this cookies does not require the user's agreed neither its management.

COOKIE	TYPE	DURATION	DESCRIPTION
_pk_id.18.b944		1 year 27 days	This cookie is installed by Matomo. The cookie is used to calculate visitor, session, campaign data and keep track of site usage for the site's analytics report. The cookies store information anonymously and assign a randomly generated number to identify unique visitors.
_pk_ses.18.b944		30 minutes	Session cookies used to temporarily store data for the visit
CONSENT		2 years	YouTube sets this cookie via embedded YouTube-videos and registers anonymous statistical data.
cookielawinfo-checkbox-advertisement		1 year	Set by the GDPR Cookie Consent plugin, this cookie is used to record the user consent for the cookies in the "Advertisement" category .
cookielawinfo-checkbox-analytics	0	11 months	This cookie is set by GDPR Cookie Consent plugin. The cookie is used to store the user consent for the cookies in the category "Analytics".
cookielawinfo-checkbox-functional	0	11 months	The cookie is set by GDPR cookie consent to record the user consent for the cookies in the category "Functional".
cookielawinfo-checkbox-necessary	0	11 months	This cookie is set by GDPR Cookie Consent plugin. The cookies is used

COOKIE	TYPE	DURATION	DESCRIPTION
			to store the user consent for the cookies in the category “Necessary”.
cookieinfo-checkbox-others	0	11 months	This cookie is set by GDPR Cookie Consent plugin. The cookie is used to store the user consent for the cookies in the category “Other”.
cookieinfo-checkbox-performance	0	11 months	This cookie is set by GDPR Cookie Consent plugin. The cookie is used to store the user consent for the cookies in the category “Performance”.
elementor		never	This cookie is used by the website’s WordPress theme. It allows the website owner to implement or change the website’s content in real-time.
viewed_cookie_policy	0	11 months	The cookie is set by the GDPR Cookie Consent plugin and is used to store whether or not user has consented to the use of cookies. It does not store any personal data.
VISITOR_INFO1_LIVE		5 months 27 days	A cookie set by YouTube to measure bandwidth that determines whether the user gets the new or old player interface.
YSC		session	YSC cookie is set by Youtube and is used to track the views of embedded videos on Youtube pages.
yt-remote-connected-devices		never	YouTube sets this cookie to store the video preferences of the user using embedded YouTube video.
yt-remote-device-id		never	YouTube sets this cookie to store the video preferences of the user using embedded YouTube video.

14.4 How do you disable cookies in a browser?

The cookies set up is directly reflected in the browser used, however here are additional information about how the user can adjust the settings in their browser so as not to accept the use of cookies, in which case the user would not have customized browsing experience. Choosing this setting may result in certain parts of the website not being accessible, as this may cause less effective browsing.

Most browsers currently allow the user to choose whether they want to accept cookies and which types. These settings are usually found in the “settings” or “preferences” in your browser’s menu.

Depending on the browser used by the user and its functionalities used may suppose the installation of cookies that are considered as a Third-party cookie. For example, in case of user choosing Google’s browser and using its translate tool of the full website, Google install its own cookies in the user’s computers which are not managed by the website publisher as well as has not liability about them. The settings of the browser cookies should be done by the user directly at the browser website.

These are the instructions to change the cookie settings in the main browsers:

These are the instructions to change the cookie settings in the main browsers:

- Information about cookies for [Mozilla Firefox](#).
- Information about cookies for [Internet Explorer](#)
- Information about cookies for [Opera](#).
- Information about cookies for [Google Chrome](#).
- Information about cookies for [Safari](#)

14.5 Further information

Further information about cookies as well as how to block them at www.allaboutcookies.org, www.youronlinechoices.eu. For any questions or comments about this website cookies, shall contact by email to info@eurecat.org as a web publisher or as a web service supplier.

15. ANNEX E: Shift2Zero legal warning

In compliance with Law 34/2002 of 11 July on Information Society and Electronic Commerce Services, the User is informed that the owner of the website www.shift2zero-project.eu is FUNDACIÓ EURECAT, whose identification information is as follows:

Registered office: Av. Universitat Autònoma, 23

Post code: 08290

Town/City: Cerdanyola del Vallès

Province: Barcelona

CIF: G66210345

E-mail: legal@eurecat.org / info@eurecat.org

Registry data: Registered in the Foundations Registry of the Generalitat de Catalunya with the number 2826.

15.1 Access to the website

This legal notice regulates the access and use of the website by Users and aims to inform about the services and products of the entity and allow general access for all Internet users.

Any person who accesses or uses the Website is considered a User and accepts, without reservations of any kind, each and every one of these general conditions, as well as of other special conditions that, if applicable, govern the use of the Portal or the services linked to it.

The User must carefully read the Legal Notice and the Privacy and Cookies Policies when they intend to use the Website, since FUNDACIÓ EURECAT reserves the right to make, at any time and without prior notice, any modification or update of the contents and services, of the present provisions for access and use and, in general, of all the elements that comprise the design and configuration of its Website. If you do not accept the conditions of access and use, please refrain from using the Website and its content.

15.2 Use of the website

The User undertakes to make diligent use of the Website, as well as the information relating to its services and/or activities, in full compliance with the applicable regulations, ethics and generally accepted good practices and law and order, the conditions of access and use and any other conditions established on the Website.

In addition, the user agrees to refrain from using any of the content for illegal purposes or effects, prohibited in this document, which may be harmful to the rights and interests of third parties, or that in any way may damage, disable, overload, deteriorate or prevent the normal use of the content (hardware and software) of other Users or of any Internet user in general.

15.3 Operation of the website

In the event of non-compliance with the conditions of the Legal Notice, or the Privacy and Cookies Policies, FUNDACIÓ EURECAT reserves the right to limit, suspend and/or exclude access to its website, adopting any technical measure necessary in this respect. FUNDACIÓ EURECAT will do everything possible to keep the website in good working order, preventing faults, or repairing them and keeping the contents up to date. However, FUNDACIÓ EURECAT does not guarantee the availability and continuity of access to the Website or the absence of errors in the content.

15.4 Liability

The User is solely liable for the use that they may make of any information or mechanism of the Website.

FUNDACIÓ EURECAT will not be liable for any damage to the hardware and/or software of the User that may arise from access and use of the Website. Likewise, it will be not liable for damages or losses that may be caused by accessing and/or using the information on the Website, and specifically those that may occur in computer systems or those caused by computer viruses/attacks, crashes, interruptions, absence or defects in connectivity and/or the Internet.

The User will be liable for the damages and/or losses that FUNDACIÓ EURECAT may suffer as a result of the breach of any of the obligations to which they are subject to through this Legal Notice, applicable regulations and the Privacy and Cookies Policies.

15.5 Policy on links

Web linking:

Third parties who intend to include a link on this website must comply with current legislation and may not host content that is inappropriate, illegal, pornographic, violent, etc.

FUNDACIÓ EURECAT will in no case be liable for the content of that Website, nor promote, guarantee, supervise or recommend the content therein.

If the linking Website fails to comply with any of the above aspects, it will be obliged to delete the link immediately.

Linking website:

This Website may include links to third-party websites that allow the User to access them. Nonetheless, FUNDACIÓ EURECAT is not liable for the content of these linked websites, but rather the User will be responsible for accepting and verifying access each time they connect.

These links or mentions have a use that does not imply the support, approval, commercialization or any relationship of this website and the persons or entities that own the site where they are located.

15.6 Intellectual and industrial property rights of the content

FUNDACIÓ EURECAT, or its licensors, are holders of all intellectual property rights over the Contents of the Website, understood as all the designs, databases, underlying computer programs (source code, included), as well as the different elements that make up the Website (texts, graphics, photographs, videos, colours, etc.), structure, layout, etc. The trademarks and trade names (“distinctive signs”) are owned by FUNDACIÓ EURECAT or the licensors.

The use of the Website by the User does not imply the transfer of any intellectual or industrial property rights. The User is totally prohibited from reproducing, copying, distributing, making available or publicly communicating, transforming or modifying the Contents or Distinctive Signs in any way, unless the authorization of the owner of the corresponding rights is granted or it is legally permitted.

15.7 Applicable legislation

The Legal Notice will be governed and interpreted in accordance with Spanish legislation. Any conflict that may arise from accessing the website will be submitted to the relevant courts or tribunals for resolution in accordance with consumer and user regulations.

15.8 Contact

For any questions or comments on this Legal Notice you can contact us at legal@eurecat.org.

